

Deliverable D9.3 Best practices documents on data standards - relates to task 9.3

Project Title (Grant agreement no.):	ELIXIR-CONVERGE: Connect and align ELIXIR Nodes to deliver sustainable FAIR life-science data management services (871075)		
Project Acronym (EC Call):	ELIXIR-CONVERGE (H2020-INFRADEV-2018-2020)		
WP No & Title:	WP9 Mobilisation of SARS-CoV-2 variant surveillance data tracking services and tools		
WP leader(s):	Aitana Neves (SIB) & Erik Hjerde (UiT) & Isabel Cuesta (ISCIII)		
Deliverable Lead Beneficiary:	ISCIII		
Contractual delivery date:	31/07/2023	Actual delivery date:	24/07/2023
Delayed:	No		
Partner(s) contributing to this deliverable:	ISCIII, SIB, UU, FPS, CNRS, UT, UiT		
<p>Authors: Sara Monzón Fernández (ISCIII), Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström (UU), María Lara (FPS), Isabel Cuesta de la Plaza (ISCIII)</p> <p>Contributors: Aitana Neves (SIB), Anliat Mohamed (CNRS), David Salgado (CNRS), Diana Pilvar (UT), Heleri Inno (UT), Imane Messak (CNRS), Jacques van Helden (CNRS), Nils-Peder Willassen (UiT), Thomas Denecker (CRNS), Robert Pergl (CTU-UOCHB), Marek Suchánek (CTU-UOCHB)</p> <p>Acknowledgments (not grant participants): Kim Ng (STATENS SERUM INSTITUT, Denmark)</p>			
Reviewers:	ELIXIR-CONVERGE Management Board (MB) members.		

Log of changes

DATE	Mvm	Who	Description
07/06/2023	0v1	Sara Monzón (ISCIII)	Initial version
10/07/2023	0v2	Sara Monzón (ISCIII)	Sent to PMO after incorporating internal WP feedback
11/07/2023	0v3	Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	Circulated to the MB for final review before submission

21/07/2023	0v4	Sara Monzón (ISCIII)	MB comments addressed
24/07/2023	1v0	Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	Final version to be uploaded into EC Portal

Table of contents

1. Executive Summary	2
2. Contribution toward project objectives	3
3. Introduction	5
4. Description of work accomplished	6
4.1 Workshop on Fair Data Point	6
4.2 Workshop on data standards for SARS-Cov-2	6
4.3 Data standards task force	7
4.4 Workshops and documentation on pathogen genomics data management	7
5. Results	8
5.1 Variant/Lineage metadata standardisation	8
5.2 Comparison of GISAID, ENA and PHA4GE data specification	8
5.3 Metadata standards survey results	10
5.4 Data standards documentation in RMDkit	12
6. Conclusions	12
7. Impact	13
8. Next Steps	13
9. Deviation from Description of Action	14

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable pertains to task 9.3, which is dedicated to the establishment of data standards for SARS-CoV-2 variants and lineages. It plays a crucial role in the development of a network of specialised data experts in SARS-CoV-2 genomic surveillance, contributing to the objectives of WP1 and WP8. Furthermore, it aligns with WP2, focusing on training and capacity building initiatives.

The accomplished work encompasses a workshop centred around the Fair Data Point concept, exploring its potential in advancing the goals of WP9. Additionally, a workshop addressing SARS-CoV-2 data standards was conducted, covering essential aspects such as metadata standards and variant/lineage nomenclature. A dedicated data standards task force was formed, which conducted a comprehensive survey to gauge the adoption of the proposed standards among participating countries within CONVERGE WP9. Furthermore, a separate task force dedicated to pathogen genomics data management collaborated with other projects, contributing to the development of valuable resources aimed at facilitating efficient data sharing.

Overall, these endeavours represent significant progress in the establishment of robust data standards and effective data management practices within the project, ultimately contributing to enhanced genomic surveillance of SARS-CoV-2.

Regarding variant and lineage nomenclature, Nextclade and Pangolin are widely adopted tools for variant classification. Integrating both tools in a comprehensive data hub allows for a thorough understanding of the genetic diversity of SARS-CoV-2. The data standards task force compared the metadata requirements of GISAID, ENA, and PHA4GE, revealing differences in the number and specificity of fields. The comparison showed that PHA4GE had the most comprehensive set of fields, while GISAID and ENA had unique fields specific to their databases. Harmonising metadata specifications and promoting interoperability remain essential challenges. The survey on metadata availability and public accessibility highlighted disparities among countries, emphasising the need for standardised metadata across the network.

2. Contribution toward project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

Objective no. / Key Result no. Description	Contributed to:
Objective 1: Develop a sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support by leveraging national capabilities (WP1, WP5)	
Key Result 1.1: Established European expert network of data stewards that connect national data centres and similar infrastructures and drive the development of interoperable solutions following international best practice, including national interpretations of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	Yes
Key Result 1.2: Development of joint guidelines and common toolkit that are adopted into funder recommendations, with support available nationally and in local languages	No
Key Result 1.3: The catalogue of successful national business models incorporated into national strategies	No
Key Result 1.4: The developed “sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support” is adopted into national ELIXIR Node	No
Objective 2: Strengthen Europe’s data management capacity through a comprehensive training programme delivered throughout the European Research Area (WP2, WP6)	
Key Result 2.1: A comprehensive ELIXIR Training and Capacity building programme in Data Management, directed at both data managers and ELIXIR users, and connected to the national training programmes in Data Management in the ELIXIR Nodes and prospective ELIXIR Member countries.	No
Key Result 2.2: Development of a collective group of trainers that support scalable deployment of Data Management training across ELIXIR Nodes.	No
Key Result 2.3: A substantial cohort of data managers, Node coordinators and researchers with specific data management skills, business planning and knowledge of transnational operations across the ELIXIR Nodes	No
Objective 3: Align national data management standards and services through a sustainable, scalable and cost-effective data management toolkit (WP2, WP3, WP5)	

Key Result 3.1: Assemble a full-stack harmonised common toolkit comprising all aspects of data management: from data capture, annotation, and sharing; to integration with analysis platforms and making the data publicly available according to international standards.	No
Key Result 3.2: Provide exemplar toolkit configurations for prioritised demonstrators to serve as templates for future use.	No
Key Result 3.3: Establish national capacity in using as well as updating, extending and sustaining the toolkit across the ERA.	No
Key Result 3.4: Enable 'FAIR at source' practice for data generation, and analytical process pipeline implementation by flexible deployment of the toolkit in national operations	No
Objective 4: Align national investments to drive local impact and global influence of ELIXIR (WP4,WP6)	
Key Result 4.1: Development of a Node Impact Assessment Toolkit based on RI-PATHS methodology.	No
Key Result 4.2: Adoption of Impact assessment in ELIXIR Nodes, supported by Node coordinators network and feedback on applicability from dialogues with national funders.	No
Key Result 4.3: Creation of national public-private partnerships and industry outreach where open life-science data and services stimulate local bioeconomy	No
Key Result 4.4: Growth in reach, impact and engagement of stakeholder communication assessed by established ELIXIR Communications metrics	No
Key Result 4.5: Initiating and advancing discussions on Membership (EU and international) or strategic partnerships (international countries) following ELIXIR-CONVERGE workshops.	No
Objectives - WP9 - Mobilisation of SARS-CoV-2 variant surveillance data tracking services and tools	
09.1 Coordinate nascent and established national data hubs focusing on brokering services to define and foster common best practices	No
09.2 Mobilise open SARS-CoV-2 genome data into the COVID-19 Data Platform (https://www.covid19dataportal.org) from individual data hubs.	No
09.3 Catalyse agreement on SARS-CoV-2 data standards for variants and lineages.	Yes
09.4 Drive development of SARS-CoV-2 variant analysis tools.	No

3. Introduction

This deliverable is associated with task 9.3, which focuses on establishing data standards for SARS-CoV-2 variants and lineages. It has strong connections to WP8 and is also related to WP1, as it aims to build a network of data experts specialising in SARS-CoV-2 genomic surveillance. Additionally, it aligns with WP2, which focuses on training and capacity building.

Data standards play a crucial role in facilitating effective analysis and sharing of SARS-CoV-2 genomic data. They establish common formats, terminologies, and protocols, ensuring consistency, compatibility, and reproducibility across research groups and platforms. By enabling the integration, comparison, and aggregation of diverse datasets, data standards empower researchers to derive meaningful insights and make informed decisions. Furthermore, data standards enhance data interoperability, promoting seamless collaboration and resource sharing among global researchers. This accelerates the pace of scientific discoveries and facilitates public health interventions. The FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) provide a comprehensive framework for addressing the challenges associated with analysing and sharing SARS-CoV-2 genomic data.

Within subtask 9.3.1, standards related to SARS-CoV-2 data variation calling and variant lineage nomenclature hold special significance. Additionally, in subtask 9.3.2, the use of ontologies and controlled vocabularies for metadata is imperative to adhere to the FAIR principles and ensure proper data sharing.

National and regional hubs collect metadata in various forms, which are then submitted to the ENA using the ERC000033 checklist or the ERC000036 for wastewater samples. This checklist includes both compulsory and recommended fields. Currently, many of these fields are in free text format. However, at local hubs, the data are likely stored in a structured form using ontologies and controlled vocabularies. Alongside ENA, GISAID serves as the main repository for globally sharing viral genomes, following its own data model for data submission. Additionally, the Public Health Alliance for Genomic Epidemiology (PHA4GE) is a collaborative initiative focused on utilising genomics to combat SARS-CoV-2 and other infectious diseases. By promoting data sharing, standardised protocols, and collaborative research, PHA4GE brings together stakeholders such as public health agencies, researchers, and data scientists. One of its contributions is the development of a SARS-CoV-2 contextual data specification, which includes a metadata collection template, reference guides, controlled vocabulary, and mapping to existing standards. The initiative employs the GENEPIO ontology, specifically designed for capturing genomic epidemiology knowledge related to infectious diseases, to ensure standardised vocabulary usage. The intersection between the GISAID, PHA4GE, and ENA Data Models serves as a global platform for sharing SARS-CoV-2 genomic data.

Within the scope of task 9.3, WP9 has facilitated community discussions, organised workshops, and established task forces to foster agreement and evaluate the implementation of best practices regarding data sharing standards.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Workshop on Fair Data Point

CONVERGE WP9, in collaboration with ELIXIR CZ – UOCHB (FIT CTU), organised a workshop on the Fair Data Point concept. The workshop took place on November 5, 2021, and saw the participation of more than 15 attendees.

The [FAIR Data Point](https://www.fairdatapoint.org/)¹ (FDP) is the practical realisation of the vision put forth by a group of authors in the [original paper on FAIR](https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18)² principles. It outlines how (meta)data can be presented on the web, using existing standards, to adhere to the principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability. The FDP comprises a specification and a reference implementation.

The primary objective of this workshop was to explore how FDP can contribute to the achievement of WP9 goals. The organisers introduced the concept of FDP, explained its architecture, and showcased its practical applications through a case study of [VODAN-in-a-box](https://www.gofairfoundation.org/vodan-in-a-box-the-all-in-one-solution-for-easy-installment-of-vodan-fair-data-points/)³. The presentation stimulated an engaging discussion among the participants, which led to the formulation of next steps and action items. For further details, discussions, and access to the slides presented during the workshop, please refer to this [link](https://docs.google.com/document/d/1RvkUwviMCzbDm8-b3K9igNzpFD2P3qvszFb5isp93k0/edit?usp=sharing)⁴.

4.2 Workshop on data standards for SARS-Cov-2

A workshop on data standards for SARS-CoV-2 was held on November 16, 2021. The workshop brought together more than 30 participants and covered key topics related to task 9.3, focusing on SARS-CoV-2 metadata standards, with a specific emphasis on challenges and issues related to variant and lineage nomenclature. The agenda of the workshop included the following sessions:

- PHA4GE: Navigating the complexities of SARS-CoV-2 data standards (Emma Griffiths) - 25 minutes
- Clinical data standards (Lyndon Zass) - 5 minutes
- Introduction to SARS-CoV-2 variant/lineage naming (Tulio De Oliveira) - 10 minutes
- Mapping between nomenclatures: Variants, Lineages, Clades, tracking SARS-CoV-2 (Emma Hodcroft) - 5 minutes
- Structuring data in practice - some thoughts (Aitana Lebrand) - 5 minutes
- Question and Answer session - 10 minutes

¹<https://www.fairdatapoint.org/>

²<https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

³<https://www.gofairfoundation.org/vodan-in-a-box-the-all-in-one-solution-for-easy-installment-of-vodan-fair-data-points/>

⁴<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1RvkUwviMCzbDm8-b3K9igNzpFD2P3qvszFb5isp93k0/edit?usp=sharing>

During the workshop, the PHA4GE consortium presented its SARS-CoV-2 contextual specification. The workshop also included a follow-up discussion, which laid the groundwork for the data standard task force. The slides and details of the workshop can be found in this [folder](#)⁵.

4.3 Data standards task force

A dedicated task force consisting of 8 members was established to address the topic of data standards. The task force focused on the themes and points discussed during the organised workshops related to task 9.3. It quickly became evident that a crucial aspect was to determine the extent to which the proposed data standards were adopted by the participating countries in CONVERGE WP9.

To contribute to this deliverable, the task force devised a survey that was distributed to all participants in CONVERGE WP9. This survey encompassed all the fields outlined in the PHA4GE contextual specification. Participating countries were requested to indicate whether they collected each metadata field in their data hub and whether the collected metadata was publicly available. By utilising the PHA4GE contextual specification, the task force was able to establish how the metadata aligned and intersected among the data models employed by ENA, GISAID, and the PHA4GE specification.

Detailed records of the meetings and discussions held by the data standards task force can be accessed via the provided [link](#)⁶.

4.4 Workshops and documentation on pathogen genomics data management

The RDMkit task force focused on consolidating experiences from the project partners and converging on a set of best-practices for human pathogen genomics data management. The task force collected references to existing documentation produced by partners, authorities and communities and selected a list of resources to reference at different stages of the data life cycle. The resources include ontologies, controlled vocabularies and data protection considerations to support timely and efficient data sharing and covers information about biological samples, experimental protocols and procedures, as well as the resulting data files and their content.

The task force worked with ELIXIR CONVERGE WP3 to develop content for a new domain page on human pathogen genomics for ELIXIR's Research Data Management Toolkit (RDMkit). The task force also participated in the BY-COVID project's Infectious Diseases Toolkit workshop held in Ghent, Belgium in May 2023 to describe the important aspects of metadata and documentation for pathogen characterisation. Partners from Sweden, Norway and Estonia also worked with the Nordic Pandemic Research Infrastructure (PaRI) project to develop a guide to SARS-CoV-2 genome data sharing.

⁵<https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1bWQElasGeAa6Dft1eT3w-CNI6H9hbxC>

⁶<https://docs.google.com/document/u/0/d/12f2KurzymwUtvfWXSLUKyitTmjf10YQIAI2DD4ZDyOI/edit>

5. Results

5.1 Variant/Lineage metadata standardisation

SARS-CoV-2 variant and lineage nomenclature plays a crucial role in tracking and understanding the evolution of the virus. As discussed in the data standards workshop, two widely adopted tools for variant classification are Nextstrain's Nextclade and Pangolin. Nextclade utilises genomic data to identify variants, predict clades, and annotate mutations, providing valuable insights into viral characteristics. On the other hand, Pangolin focuses specifically on assigning lineages to SARS-CoV-2 sequences based on shared genetic markers.

To ensure comprehensive data analysis in a data hub, it is recommended to incorporate both Nextclade and Pangolin. By leveraging Nextclade's variant analysis and Pangolin's lineage assignment, the data hub can provide a comprehensive overview of the genetic diversity of SARS-CoV-2. Integrating these tools enables researchers and public health officials to track the spread and impact of specific variants and lineages, contributing to effective surveillance and response strategies.

5.2 Comparison of GISAID, ENA and PHA4GE data specification

The data standards task force had a goal of assessing the metadata requirements of main public databases receiving SARS-CoV-2 data. To achieve this, the task force compared the submission forms used by ENA ([ERC000033](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/ERC000033)⁷, ENA virus pathogen reporting standard checklist) and [GISAID](https://gisaid.org/)⁸ with the [SARS-CoV-2 contextual specification](https://github.com/pha4ge/SARS-CoV-2-Contextual-Data-Specification)⁹ developed by the PHA4GE initiative. The PHA4GE specification served as a comprehensive data model, including a majority of the recommended fields for SARS-CoV-2 genomic surveillance.

The comparison involved mapping each field in the three specifications, utilising the databases field descriptions and the ontology annotations provided by PHA4GE. Mapping results can be found in the provided [link](#)¹⁰. **Figure 1** illustrates the notable discrepancies in the number of required, recommended or optional fields: 26, 65 and 132 for GISAID, ENA and PHA4GE respectively. However, after mapping the fields, a more comparable quantity of information was obtained: 64 for GISAID, 88 for ENA, and 137 for PHA4GE. This suggests that different databases solicit information to varying degrees of generality, wherein one field in one database may encompass multiple fields in others.

⁷<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/ERC000033>

⁸<https://gisaid.org/>

⁹<https://github.com/pha4ge/SARS-CoV-2-Contextual-Data-Specification>

¹⁰<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1Qehkcml1WFwE9n2rBiloAmlLLwzPT4hb/edit?usp=sharing&oid=114088100290741425598&rtpof=true&sd=true>

Figure 1: Number of fields included in GISAID, ENA and GISAID data models.

The comparison, depicted in **Figure 2**, revealed that the three data specifications shared 37 concepts across different degrees of generalisation and hierarchy. Only three fields were exclusive to GISAID, primarily consisting of free text or database identifiers such as "submitting_lab_sample_id," "treatment," and "type." Similarly, ENA had 28 unique fields, predominantly related to specific fields like "library_strategy," "library_layout," and identifiers/accessions such as "experiment_accession" and "run_alias."

Figure 2: Venn diagram comparing interaction of fields between GISAID, ENA and PHA4GE specifications.

In contrast, the PHA4GE specification boasted 66 fields that were distinct, making it the most comprehensive set. Notably, PHA4GE employed structured fields, offering a predefined set of potential values for each field. These findings indicate that interoperability is more feasible between PHA4GE and ENA or GISAID, rather than in the reverse direction.

While the results demonstrate that most of the information is present across all metadata sets, achieving interoperability poses challenges, particularly in terms of proper ontology annotation with a robust concept hierarchy.

5.3 Metadata standards survey results

A comprehensive survey was conducted to ascertain the availability of genomic metadata fields in the public domain for each participating country. The survey specifically targeted fields outlined by the PHA4GE initiative, including the annotation with the GENEPIO ontology to provide concise and explicit descriptions, ensuring data standardisation. The checklist encompassed a range of mandatory and optional fields, including sensitive data concerning the host.

The study's findings lay the groundwork for establishing new guidelines regarding the inclusion of fields in checklists and their mandatory status. The survey gathered responses from five different countries, and the detailed results can be accessed through the provided [link](#)¹¹.

The survey conducted inquiring about the availability and public accessibility of metadata fields yielded insightful results, which are summarised in two figures. **Figure 3A** demonstrates that Denmark and Spain possess a higher number of available fields (approximately 80 out of 132), but only 25 fields are available across all surveyed countries.

Notably, the differences become more pronounced when examining the publicly available data, as depicted in **Figure 3B**. Here, we observe that merely 6 fields are commonly shared among all 5 countries. These findings highlight the disparity in field sharing and underscore the need for harmonising the metadata specification utilised by countries within the network. This provides a clear direction for the next steps to be taken by the community established in this particular work package.

¹¹<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1IFwhxp51hmSebitlCxLVyr4vxWRxJJZy7s9teA-ffBc/edit#gid=1822412352>

Figure 3: A) UpSet diagram comparing the survey results for the **available** metadata fields for each country. B) UpSet diagram comparing the survey results for the **published** metadata fields for each country.

5.4 Data standards documentation in RMDkit

The RDMkit task force created a new resource to support human pathogen data management and submissions as a domain page on Human Pathogen Genomics in ELIXIR's Research Data Management Toolkit (RDMkit)—[pending review](#)¹² by the RDMkit editorial board at the time of writing. The resources collected from across the project partners and collaborators were consolidated to address use-cases around planning, data collection and data sharing in research studies and public surveillance initiatives focusing on human pathogens and variants. The following extract from the introduction section describes the scope and focus of the resource:

“The human pathogen genomics domain focuses on studying the genetic code of organisms that cause disease in humans. Studies to identify and understand pathogens are conducted across different types of organisations ranging from research institutes to regional public health authorities. The aims can include urgent outbreak response, prevention measures, and developing remedies such as treatments and vaccines.

Data management challenges in this domain include the potential urgency of data sharing and secondary use of data across initiatives emerging from research, public health and policy. While the pathogenic organisms are the object of interest, there are many considerations to account for when dealing with samples collected from patients, pathogen surveillance, and human research subjects.

The genomic data can represent anything from the genetic sequence of a single pathogen isolate to various fragments of genetic materials from a flora of pathogens in a larger population. Other data can represent a wide range of contextual information about the human host, the disease, and various environmental factors.”

The content was organised under three major sections highlighting and addressing a selection of concerns that were identified during and following the workshops and collaborations described in section 4.4. The resource was designed to present and outline solutions with links to complementary and authoritative resources across other sections of the RDMkit, such as the general sections on human data, data brokering and data publication, and resources maintained externally, such as the FAIR Cookbook resource maintained by ELIXIR and other resources maintained by ECDC, Genomic Standards Consortium (GSC), and the GenEpiO Consortium. Each solution contextualises and highlights relevant standards, *de facto* standards, or recommendations with regards to data and metadata. The following summary of the major sections provides an overview of the considerations and solutions covered by the resources:

¹²<https://github.com/elixir-europe/rdmkit/pull/1263>

Planning a study with pathogen genomic data

Major considerations

- What legal and ethical aspects do you need to consider?
- What public health and research initiatives should you consider aligning with?
- What conventions will you adopt when planning your study?

Solutions presented include *Working with human data*, *Isolating pathogen from host associated information*, *Interacting with public health initiatives*, and *Planning sequencing experiments*.

Collecting and processing pathogen genomic data

Major considerations

- What information should you consider recording when collecting data?
- What data and file formats should you consider for your project?
- What existing data will you integrate or use as a reference in your project?

Solutions presented include *Filtering genomic reads corresponding to human DNA fragments*, *Capturing contextual information about the sample*, and *Generating genomic data*.

Sharing and preserving pathogen genomic data

Major considerations include:

- What data need to be preserved by the project and for how long?
- What is preserved by others and how would someone find and access the data?
- What databases should I use to share human pathogen genomics data?
- What other research information (such as protocols, computational tools, samples) can the project share?

Solutions presented include *Sharing host related and other contextual information* and *Sharing pathogen genomic data*.

While working on this resource, the Infectious Diseases Toolkit (IDTk) being developed for the BY-COVID project was recognised as an emerging resource and authority for more extensive content on the topic. The RDMkit task force also contributed to the *Data description* section envisioned for the IDTk topic on *Pathogen characterisation* and contacts have been established to address unintentional overlaps and future links across the resources. The three subsections drafted as a collaborative effort across BY-COVID and ELIXIR CONVERGE cover *Good practices for describing data in general*, and specific guidance on describing *Biological samples*, and *Genome data of viral pathogens* and are [pending comments](#)¹³ by the IDTk editorial board and BY-COVID community at the time of writing

¹³<https://github.com/elixir-europe/infectious-diseases-toolkit/pull/194>

6. Conclusions

In conclusion, the standardisation of SARS-CoV-2 variant and lineage metadata is crucial for effectively tracking and understanding the virus's evolution. Nextclade and Pangolin are two widely adopted tools for variant classification, offering valuable insights into viral characteristics and lineage assignment based on genetic markers. To ensure comprehensive data sharing, it is recommended to incorporate both Nextclade and Pangolin in a data hub, enabling researchers and public health officials to monitor specific variants and lineages.

The comparison of GISAID, ENA, and PHA4GE data specifications revealed differences in the number of required, recommended, and optional fields. Mapping the fields resulted in a more comparable quantity of information across the databases. While the three specifications shared common concepts, GISAID, ENA, and PHA4GE had unique fields. PHA4GE stood out as the most comprehensive set with structured fields, facilitating interoperability with ENA and GISAID. However, achieving interoperability poses challenges, particularly in ontology annotation with a robust concept hierarchy.

The survey on metadata standards showed variations in the availability and public accessibility of genomic metadata fields among the surveyed countries. Denmark and Spain had a higher number of available fields, but only a limited number were shared across all countries. This emphasises the need for harmonising the metadata specifications within the network to improve data sharing. The survey's findings provide a foundation for establishing guidelines and determining the next steps for the community involved in this work package.

7. Impact

Our metadata survey has demonstrated the need for data harmonisation across countries, despite the existence of various ontologies and checklists, notably to define minimal sets of data to be collected or shared within appropriate ethical and legal frameworks. In addition, the documentation produced on pathogen genomic data sharing and FAIR Data Points constitute essential building blocks for capacity building by covering some key ethical, legal and technical considerations.

8. Next Steps

ELIXIR CONVERGE WP9 has successfully established a supra-national network of pathogen genomic data hubs, facilitating the sharing of data and the adoption of common best practices. Looking ahead, our vision, as described in deliverable 9.2, is to expand the scope of these data

hubs beyond SARS-CoV-2 and embrace One Health surveillance. This expansion would involve monitoring pathogens across human, veterinary, food, and environmental domains, with a focus on areas such as antimicrobial resistance and food-borne pathogens.

While we have outlined the framework for a distributed network of Pathogen Data Platforms (PDPs), the next step involves implementing the proposed concept. Specifically, two key task forces need to be established based on the conclusions drawn in this deliverable:

1. Data Standards and Quality Task Force: This task force will ensure data quality within the data hub ecosystem. It will define the metadata and data requirements for the distributed nodes, establishing compulsory minimal data sets per use case (e.g., for different pathogens) to address the disparities highlighted in this deliverable regarding data availability. Furthermore, the task force will propose controlled vocabularies and ontologies to improve and expand the existing ones. It will also define quality tags for raw and processed data and suggest benchmark datasets for validating algorithms and pipelines.
2. FAIR Task Force: Following the Fair Data Point workshop, this task force will ensure that the implemented interfaces and standards align with the latest FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) objectives. It will continuously provide suggestions for improvements and support the federated nodes in sharing open, anonymized datasets, including through platforms like ENA (European Nucleotide Archive).

By establishing these task forces, we aim to enhance data quality, interoperability, and accessibility within the network, advancing the goals of the Pathogen Data Platforms. This will foster effective collaboration in pathogen surveillance and enable us to address emerging challenges in a comprehensive and coordinated manner.

9. Deviation from Description of Action

Not applicable

